

Supplementary Information

Full Title: Impact of diabetes on clinical and safety outcomes in acute ischemic stroke patients receiving reperfusion therapy: a meta-analysis

Authors: Sian A. Bradley, Ivica Smokovski and Sonu M. M. Bhaskar*

***Corresponding author:**

Dr. Sonu M. M. Bhaskar, MD PhD - Sonu.Bhaskar@globalhealthneurolab.org

List of Contents

1. Search Strategy (Keywords/MeSH Terms)
2. Supplemental Tables
 - 2A. Supplemental Table 1. Summary of significant meta-analysis outcomes
 - 2B. Supplemental Table 2. Summary data and performance estimates for selectivity and specificity analysis
 - 2C. Supplemental Table 3. Jaded analysis for methodological quality/risk of bias and test for funding bias
 - 2D. Supplemental Table 4. Egger's test for publication bias assessment of the included studies
 - 2E. Supplemental Table 5. MOOSE Checklist for meta-analyses of observational studies included in the study
 - 2F. Supplemental Table 6. PRISMA checklist for the meta-analysis
 - 2G. Supplemental Table 7. STARD-2015 Checklist for prognostic studies
3. Supplemental Figures
 - 3A. Supplemental Figure 1. Funnel plots of estimated effect for the association of diabetes with clinical outcomes including: (A) functional outcome at 90 days and (B) functional outcome at discharge, (C) mortality at 90 days, (D) poor recanalization status, (E) symptomatic intracerebral haemorrhage, and (F) haemorrhagic transformation.

3B. Supplemental Figure 2. Egger's tests of effect sizes for studies on association of diabetes with: (A) functional outcome at 90 days and (B) functional outcome at discharge, (C) mortality at 90 days, (D) poor recanalization status, (E) symptomatic intracerebral haemorrhage, and (F) haemorrhagic transformation.

3C. Supplemental Figure 3. The sensitivity and specificity of diabetes as a prognostic modality in (A) functional outcome at 90 days, (B) functional outcome at discharge, (C) Mortality at 90 days, (D) recanalization status, (E) symptomatic intracerebral haemorrhage) and (F) haemorrhagic transformation.

3D. Supplemental Figure 4. Likelihood ratio scatter matrix for diabetes and (A) functional outcome at 90 days, (B) functional outcome at discharge, (C) Mortality at 90 days, (D) recanalization status, (E) symptomatic intracerebral haemorrhage) and (F) haemorrhagic transformation.

3E. Supplemental Figure 5. Forest plots of sensitivity of each included study: Influence of a single study in meta-analysis for association of diabetes with (A) functional outcome, (B) mortality, (C) symptomatic intracerebral haemorrhage, (D) haemorrhagic transformation.

3F. Supplemental Figure 6. Effect size analyses for the association of diabetes with (A) functional outcome, (B) mortality, (C) symptomatic intracerebral haemorrhage, (D) haemorrhagic transformation.

1. Search Strategy (Keywords/MeSH Terms)

(Stroke OR Stroke care OR acute stroke OR Cerebrovascular Accident OR Brain ischemia OR Brain Ischemia OR ischemic stroke OR AIS OR acute ischemic stroke anterior circulation OR MCA Stroke OR ICA Stroke OR middle cerebral artery occlusion OR MCA occlusion OR ICA occlusion OR large vessel occlusion OR LVO OR cerebral infarction) AND (Reperfusion OR endovascular thrombectomy OR endovascular treatment OR acute stroke treatment OR acute stroke intervention OR thrombolysis OR tPA OR tissue plasminogen activator OR IVT OR IV tPA OR IV rTPA OR thrombectomy OR EVT OR clot retrieval OR systemic thrombolysis OR mechanical thrombectomy OR endovascular procedure) AND (diabetes OR diabetes mellitus OR type 2 diabetes OR T2DM) NOT myocardial infarction NOT heart failure NOT coronary

2. Supplemental Tables

2A. Supplemental Table 1. Summary of significant meta-analysis outcomes

	Poor functional outcome at 90 days	Poor functional outcome at discharge	Mortality at 90 days	Poor post-reperfusion recanalization	Symptomatic intracerebral haemorrhage	Haemorrhagic transformation
Overall	Significant	Significant	Significant	Not significant	Significant	Significant
ST	Significant	N/A	Significant	Significant	Significant	Significant
EVT	Significant	N/A	Not significant	N/R	Significant	N/A

2B. Supplemental Table 2. Summary data and performance estimates for selectivity and specificity analysis

	mRS at 90 days N (95% CI)	mRS at discharge N (95% CI)	Mortality N (95% CI)	Recanalization N (95% CI)	sICH N (95% CI)
Sensitivity	0.59 (0.54 – 0.64)	0.61 (0.47 - 0.73)	0.23 (0.20 – 0.26)	0.70 (0.45 – 0.86)	0.04 (0.03 - 0.06)
Specificity	0.50 (0.46 – 0.55)	0.46 (0.33 - 0.59)	0.85 (0.82 – 0.88)	0.48 (0.29 – 0.67)	0.97 (0.96 - 0.98)
ROC Area, AUROC	0.56 (0.03 - 0.98)	0.54 (0.04 - 0.98)	0.54 (0.01 – 0.99)	0.61 (0.06 – 0.98)	0.42 (0.00 -1.00)
PLR	1.2 (1.1 - 1.3)	1.1 (1.0 - 1.2)	1.6 (1.5 - 1.7)	1.3 (1.0 – 1.7)	1.4 (1.2 - 1.7)
NLR	0.82 (0.75 - 0.88)	8.6 (0.76 - 0.98)	0.90 (0.89 - 0.92)	0.64 (0.40 – 1.01)	0.99 (0.98 - 0.99)
Prognostic Odds Ratio	1 (1 - 2)	1 (1 - 2)	2 (2 - 2)	2 (1 - 4)	1 (1 - 2)
AIC	229.3	86.4	132.9	68.1	168.1
BIC	235.2	86.8	136.1	68.5	173.6
Deviance	219.3	76.4	122.9	58.1	158.1
BICdiff	269.4	103.7	69.0	65.2	195.8
Correlation (Mixed Model)	-0.91	-0.99	-1.00	-0.87	-1.00
Proportion of heterogeneity likely due to threshold effect	0.83	0.98	1.00	0.76	1.00
ICC_SEN	0.02 (0.00 – 0.05)	0.08 (0.00 - 0.19)	0.02 (0.00 – 0.04)	0.22 (0.00 – 0.50)	0.05 (0.00 - 0.10)
MED_SEN	0.57 (0.54 - 0.62)	0.62 (0.56 - 0.75)	0.55 (0.52 – 0.62))	0.71 (0.60 – 0.89)	0.60 (0.56 - 0.66)
ICC_SPE	0.03 (0.00 - 0.05)	0.08 (0.00 - 0.19)	0.02 (0.00 – 0.05)	0.17 (0.00 - 0.37)	0.08 (0.01 - 0.15)
MED_SPE	0.57 (0.55 - 0.61)	0.62 (0.56 - 0.74)	0.57 (0.54 – 0.62)	0.68 (0.59 - 0.84)	0.63 (0.58 - 0.70)
Heterogeneity (Chi-square):	LRT_Q = 181.868 df =2.00, LRT_p =0.000	LRT_Q = 87.712 df =2.00, LRT_p =0.000	LRT_Q = 556.985 df =2.00, LRT_p =0.000	LRT_Q = 58316 df =2.00, LRT_p =0.000	LRT_Q = 134.586 df =2.00, LRT_p =0.000
Inconsistency (I-square)	LRT_I2 = 99, 95% CI = (98 - 99)	LRT_I2 = 98, 95% CI = (96-99)	LRT_I2 = 96, 95% CI = (94 - 99)	LRT_I2 = 97, 95% CI = (94-99)	LRT_I2 = 99, 95% CI = (98-99)
Deek's Test P Value	P=0.45	P = 0.54	P=0.47	P = 0.48	P = 0.81

Abbreviations: ICC_Sen = Interstudy variation in Sensitivity; MED_SEN - Interstudy variation in Sensitivity; ICC_SPE: Interstudy variation in Specificity; MED_SPE: Interstudy variation in Specificity; PLR:Positive Likelihood Ratio; NLR = Negative Likelihood Ratio

Supplemental Table 3. Jaded analysis for methodological quality/risk of bias and test for funding bias

	Ahmed et al.	Bauza et al.	Borggreffe et al.	Chen et al.	Cucchiara et al.	Desilles et al.	Fang et al.	Filipov et al.	Fuentes et al.	Kim et al.	Lansberg et al.	Mishra et al.	Montalvo et al.	Ngiam et al.	Nikneshan et al.	Nowak et al.	Reiter et al.	Ribo et al.	Tang et al.	Tsivgoulis et al.	Wang et al.	Wnuk et al.	Xu et al.	Yoo et al.	Zhang et al.	
Jaded Analysis																										
Was the study randomised	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Was the method of randomisation appropriate (not specified = 0)	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Was the study described as being blinded?	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Was the method of blinding appropriate	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Was there a description of withdrawals and dropouts?	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Was there a clear description of the inclusion/exclusion criteria	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1
Was the method used to assess adverse events described?	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Was the method of statistical analysis described?	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
TOTALS (MJA_ROB)	3	7	3	3	7	2	2	2	3	2	5	3	3	5	3	2	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	3	
Funding Bias	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	

2C. Supplemental Table 4. Egger’s test for publication bias assessment of the included studies

Outcome	Std_Eff	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% CI]	P
Poor functional outcome (90 days)	Slope	0.46	0.03	13.70	0.000	0.39 – 0.54	0.454
	Bias	-0.40	0.52	-0.78	0.454	-1.56 – 0.75	
Poor functional outcome (Discharge)	Slope	0.42	0.20	0.21	0.852	-0.83 – 0.91	0.405
	Bias	1.55	1.48	1.05	0.405	-4.83 – 7.94	
Mortality (90 days)	Slope	0.55	0.03	20.54	0.000	0.48 – 0.62	0.483
	Bias	-0.33	0.44	-0.76	0.483	-1.45 – 0.79	
Poor recanalization status	Slope	0.29	02.22	0.13	0.906	-9.26 – 9.85	0.869
	Bias	0.97	5.18	0.19	0.869	-21.33 – 23.27	
sICH	Slope	0.43	0.11	3.97	0.003	0.19 – 0.68	0.710
	Bias	0.22	0.57	0.38	0.710	-1.07 – 1.51	
HT	Slope	0.30	0.22	1.37	0.212	-0.22 – 0.81	0.790
	Bias	-0.21	0.75	-0.28	0.790	-1.97 – 1.56	

sICH: symptomatic intracerebral haemorrhage; HT: haemorrhagic transformation

2D. Supplemental Table 5. MOOSE Checklist for meta-analyses of observational studies included in the study

Item No	Recommendation	Reported on Page No
Reporting of background should include		
1	Problem definition	3
2	Hypothesis statement	3
3	Description of study outcome(s)	5
4	Type of exposure or intervention used	4
5	Type of study designs used	4

6	Study population	4
Reporting of search strategy should include		
7	Qualifications of searchers (eg, librarians and investigators)	1
8	Search strategy, including time period included in the synthesis and key words	3-4, supplemental info
9	Effort to include all available studies, including contact with authors	-
10	Databases and registries searched	3
11	Search software used, name and version, including special features used (eg, explosion)	-
12	Use of hand searching (eg, reference lists of obtained articles)	4
13	List of citations located and those excluded, including justification	7, table 1
14	Method of addressing articles published in languages other than English	-
15	Method of handling abstracts and unpublished studies	-
16	Description of any contact with authors	-
Reporting of methods should include		
17	Description of relevance or appropriateness of studies assembled for assessing the hypothesis to be tested	4
18	Rationale for the selection and coding of data (eg, sound clinical principles or convenience)	-
19	Documentation of how data were classified and coded (eg, multiple raters, blinding and interrater reliability)	-
20	Assessment of confounding (eg, comparability of cases and controls in studies where appropriate)	-
21	Assessment of study quality, including blinding of quality assessors, stratification, or regression on possible predictors of study results	5
22	Assessment of heterogeneity	5, table 2
23	Description of statistical methods (eg, complete description of fixed or random effects models, justification of whether the chosen models account for predictors of study results, dose-response models, or cumulative meta-analysis) in sufficient detail to be replicated	5-6
24	Provision of appropriate tables and graphics	List of tables/figures, supplemental info

Reporting of results should include		
25	Graphic summarizing individual study estimates and overall estimate	-
26	Table giving descriptive information for each study included	14-15
27	Results of sensitivity testing (eg, subgroup analysis)	6-8, table 3
28	Indication of statistical uncertainty of findings	6-8

Reporting of discussion should include		
29	Quantitative assessment of bias (eg, publication bias)	6-8
30	Justification for exclusion (eg, exclusion of non-English language citations)	4
31	Assessment of quality of included studies	Supplemental info

Reporting of conclusions should include		
32	Consideration of alternative explanations for observed results	11-12
33	Generalization of the conclusions (ie, appropriate for the data presented and within the domain of the literature review)	11
34	Guidelines for future research	-
35	Disclosure of funding source	13-14

From: Stroup DF, Berlin JA, Morton SC, et al, for the Meta-analysis Of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (MOOSE) Group. Meta-analysis of Observational Studies in Epidemiology. A Proposal for Reporting. *JAMA*. 2000;283(15):2008-2012. doi: 10.1001/jama.283.15.2008.

2E. Supplemental Table 6. PRISMA checklist for the meta-analysis

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	N/A
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist.	2
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	3
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	3
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	4
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	3-4
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers, and websites, including any filters and limits used.	Supplemental info
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	4-5
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	4-5
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g., for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.	4-5
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g., participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.	5-6
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	5-6
Effect measures	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g., risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	5
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g., tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item #5)).	-
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.	5.6

Diabetes in acute ischemic stroke

	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.	6
	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.	5-6
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g., subgroup analysis, meta-regression).	5
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	6
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	6
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	6
RESULTS			
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram.	Supplemental info
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.	-
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	Table 1
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	Supplemental info
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimates and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	7-9
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	7-9
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g., confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.	7-9
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	-
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.	Table 3
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	7-9
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	7-9
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	11-13
	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	11-13
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	11-13
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	11-13
OTHER INFORMATION			

Diabetes in acute ischemic stroke

Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state that the review was not registered.	-
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	-
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	-
Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	13-14
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	13-14
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	-

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71

2F. Supplemental Table 7. STARD-2015 Checklist for prognostic studies

Section & Topic	No	Item	Reported on page #
TITLE OR ABSTRACT			
	1	Identification as a study of diagnostic accuracy using at least one measure of accuracy (Such as sensitivity, specificity, predictive values, or AUC)	2
ABSTRACT			
	2	Structured summary of study design, methods, results, and conclusions (for specific guidance, see STARD for Abstracts)	2
INTRODUCTION			
	3	Scientific and clinical background, including the intended use and clinical role of the index test	3
	4	Study objectives and hypotheses	3
METHODS			
<i>Study design</i>	5	Whether data collection was planned before the index test and reference standard were performed (prospective study) or after (retrospective study)	-
<i>Participants</i>	6	Eligibility criteria	4
	7	On what basis potentially eligible participants were identified (such as symptoms, results from previous tests, inclusion in registry)	4
	8	Where and when potentially eligible participants were identified (setting, location and dates)	3-4
	9	Whether participants formed a consecutive, random or convenience series	-
<i>Test methods</i>	10a	Index test, in sufficient detail to allow replication	-
	10b	Reference standard, in sufficient detail to allow replication	-
	11	Rationale for choosing the reference standard (if alternatives exist)	-
	12a	Definition of and rationale for test positivity cut-offs or result categories of the index test, distinguishing pre-specified from exploratory	5
	12b	Definition of and rationale for test positivity cut-offs or result categories of the reference standard, distinguishing pre-specified from exploratory	-
	13a	Whether clinical information and reference standard results were available to the performers/readers of the index test	-
	13b	Whether clinical information and index test results were available to the assessors of the reference standard	-
<i>Analysis</i>	14	Methods for estimating or comparing measures of diagnostic accuracy	10
	15	How indeterminate index test or reference standard results were handled	-
	16	How missing data on the index test and reference standard were handled	-

	17	Any analyses of variability in diagnostic accuracy, distinguishing pre-specified from exploratory	-
	18	Intended sample size and how it was determined	-
RESULTS			
<i>Participants</i>	19	Flow of participants, using a diagram	Fig 1
	20	Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of participants	7, Table 1
	21a	Distribution of severity of disease in those with the target condition	-
	21b	Distribution of alternative diagnoses in those without the target condition	-
	22	Time interval and any clinical interventions between index test and reference standard	-
<i>Test results</i>	23	Cross tabulation of the index test results (or their distribution) by the results of the reference standard	Table 1
	24	Estimates of diagnostic accuracy and their precision (such as 95% confidence intervals)	-
	25	Any adverse events from performing the index test or the reference standard	-
DISCUSSION			
	26	Study limitations, including sources of potential bias, statistical uncertainty, and generalisability	7-9
	27	Implications for practice, including the intended use and clinical role of the index test	7-9
OTHER INFORMATION			
	28	Registration number and name of registry	-
	29	Where the full study protocol can be accessed	Main Manuscript and Supplemental Information
	30	Sources of funding and other support; role of funders	13-14

3. Supplemental Figures

3A. Supplemental Figure 1. Funnel plots of estimated effect for the association of diabetes with clinical outcomes including: (A) functional outcome at 90 days and (B) functional outcome at discharge, (C) mortality at 90 days, (D) poor recanalization status, (E) symptomatic intracerebral haemorrhage, and (F) haemorrhagic transformation

Note: Begg's funnel plot to visually detect the presence of publication bias in the meta-analysis.

3B. Supplemental Figure 2. Egger's tests of effect sizes for studies on association of diabetes with: (A) functional outcome at 90 days and (B) functional outcome at discharge, (C) mortality at 90 days, (D) poor recanalization, (E) symptomatic intracerebral haemorrhage, and (F) haemorrhagic transformation

3C. Supplemental Figure 3. The sensitivity and specificity of diabetes as a prognostic modality in (A) functional outcome at 90 days, (B) functional outcome at discharge, (C) Mortality at 90 days, (D) recanalization status and (E) symptomatic intracerebral haemorrhage

3D. Supplemental Figure 4. Likelihood ratio scatter matrix for diabetes and (A) functional outcome at 90 days, (B) functional outcome at discharge, (C) Mortality at 90 days, (D) recanalization status and (E) symptomatic intracerebral haemorrhage

3E. Supplemental Figure 5. Forest plots of sensitivity of each included study: Influence of a single study in meta-analysis for association of diabetes with (A) functional outcome, (B) mortality, (C) symptomatic intracerebral haemorrhage, (D) haemorrhagic transformation

Influence of a single study in meta-analysis estimation.
 sICH: symptomatic intracerebral haemorrhage, HT: haemorrhagic transformation

3F. Supplemental Figure 6. Effect size analyses for the association of diabetes with (A) functional outcome, (B) mortality, (C) symptomatic intracerebral haemorrhage, (D) haemorrhagic transformation

XX

Weights are from random effects model.

mRS: modified Rankin Scale, sICH: symptomatic intracerebral haemorrhage, HT: haemorrhagic transformation